

The politics of archives. An educational scenario on working with private community archives.

Background

Q is a PhD candidate, working on the history of disability in theatre and music. For their project, they engage with the remaining members of a mixed-ability cabaret group (consisting of both disabled and nondisabled people) that ran between 1975 and 1990. Q arranges an 8-person group interview with the remaining members.

The members bring their private archival materials connected to the cabaret group to the interview: photographs, music recordings, administrative documents, LPs, brochures, and so on. During the interview, the members realise the precarity of these materials. The cabaret group's archive is fragmented and at risk of dissolving completely when the remaining members pass away.

During the interview, the members suggest that Q's research project would be the perfect opportunity to combine and secure all remaining fragments of the cabaret group's archive.

Issue 1

In addition to their PhD research, Q is a disability activist who is involved in establishing a national disability archive. They realise the cabaret group's unique contributions and the precarity of the archival materials.

Questions for researchers

- Should Q disclose their involvement in establishing a national disability archive to the cabaret group members? Why/why not? How should they react to the members' idea of combining and securing the cabaret group's archive?
- In what ways can Q cope with the implicit and explicit expectations from the cabaret group members? Whom can they ask for advice?

Issue 2

Q's daily supervisor is involved in the establishment of the national disability archive as well - not in the capacity of a disability activist, but as a sympathising academic. Q's promotor, who is the PI of the PhD project, is not involved in the establishment of the national disability archive.

Questions for researchers

- What should the role of Q's supervisors be in this particular situation? What advice should they give Q in regards to taking on work that does not strictly fall within the scope of their PhD research?
- What opportunities do Q's supervisors have to support the cabaret group members' suggestion of combining and securing their archive? What are potential conflicts of interests that could arise between Q's supervisors, given their respective roles as daily supervisor and promotor/PI?

Issue 3

The cabaret group has not received any academic interest so far. All disabled members have passed away by the time of Q's research project. Only several ageing nondisabled members remain.

Questions for researchers

- What are potential ethical considerations in the establishment of an archive of the remaining materials of the cabaret group? How should ownership of the respective materials be arranged?
- What is the relevance of conserving the cabaret's group materials in terms of epistemic justice? What are potential opportunities and pitfalls? How should stakeholders navigate the fact that none of the disabled cabaret group members are able to contribute to the archive, nor determine their representation in it?